

TECHNOLOGICAL OBJECTIVE ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING THE KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT SPORTS TOURISM

Gafurov Azizbek Umarjonovich

independent researcher of Fergana State University,
Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)
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Annotation: This article describes the peculiarities of training future physical education teachers for sports tourism, opinions on the development of various reforms in society.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, continuous education, physical education teachers, innovative and digital, educational standards, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction

In connection with the development of the society, the goal orientation of the technology is clearly manifested in the following: the development of the future personnel through the development of voluntary qualities; it educates great confidence in the future and perseverance in the face of difficulties; to develop the skills and abilities to develop a sense of responsibility to ancestors and descendants, destiny, responsibility and involvement in the destiny of the individual society;

and from the point of view of an individual approach: free thinking based on self-awareness, self-development, self-improvement, self-expression by developing voluntary qualities in future physical education teachers development of skills and competencies.

The technology of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism was designed based on the conceptual foundations of a reflexive approach, and included the following stages with a goal-oriented, systematic description: analytical - future physical education science collecting, analyzing, summarizing and evaluating information on the development of teachers' knowledge of sports tourism; organizational-preparation - clarification of the prospect of technology implementation, selection of forms, methods and tools of the pedagogical process, improvement of methodological training of teachers-coaches; activity-related - step-by-step implementation of the technology of developing the knowledge of future physical education teachers about sports tourism; monitoring - evaluating the dynamics of the development of knowledge of sports tourism of future physical

education teachers, making corrections to the pedagogical process when necessary; result - evaluation of the results and clarification of future tasks of educational work.

It consists of two technological parts: substantive-procedural and organizational-pedagogical.

The content of the technology reflects the unit of cognitive - practical activity - reflection and the levels of development of volitional qualities that are manifested in each of these stages in its own way.

Materials and Methods

It is known that the means of physical education include physical exercises (including the following modules: gymnastics, athletics, sports games, general development exercises), healing forces of nature (sun, air, water) and hygienic factors (work, study, sleep, eating habits, sanitation and hygiene conditions) are relevant. Physical education tools have a wide range of opportunities for the development of willpower in future physical education teachers. But these possibilities do not materialize on their own, at the heart of this lies a systematic pedagogical process directed at a specific goal. Therefore, the author found it necessary to develop a special program for the effective application of this pedagogical process in order to develop voluntary qualities.

Dynamic endurance is developed through a variety of exercises (exercises with dumbbells, barbells, using body mass itself for buping, as well as shells and trainers, and exercises such as voluntary muscle tension with selected exercises), while performing such exercises the length of the muscles changes.

Dynamic gymnastic exercises and these exercises include dumbbells, barbells, stones, expanders, rubber bands, gymnastic shells (barbell, brusye, gymnastic wall, rings, shest, rope), the method of lifting the body's own mass (pulling on the barbell, squatting o 'squats, lifting legs and trunk while lying down) and other gymnastic exercises are the most common means of developing strength endurance.

Gymnastics using projectiles is one of the main sections of the physical education program of schools and universities. Dumbbell gymnastics is more often used during independent training. In recent times, various trainers that allow effective development of strength endurance are becoming widespread.

It is possible to achieve the necessary training effect through any type of exercise, if the appropriate parameters - intensity and volume - are provided. One of the relatively forgotten, but effective means of developing strength

endurance is free gymnastics. Doing this type of gymnastics, based on voluntary muscle tension and slow movement, will give good results.

Exercises used to develop static strength endurance include lifting objects in a certain position, being able to hold the body in a certain form (for example, while lying on the back, lifting the legs off the floor), being able to hold oneself in shells (for example, in brusers, able to keep the legs at an angle on the gymnastic wall, rings, horizontal bars), lift dumbbells, barbells, keep the body static while leaning on an immovable object, test strength with a partner, overcome the resistance of one's own muscles (for example, involves trying to bend the head back with the hands, overcoming the resistance of the neck and back muscles), stretching the muscles freely.

As a norm of static strength endurance, the ability to stand on the hands or hang, forming an angle between the legs and the body, and maintain such a position for 6 seconds (in this case, the abdominal muscles are trained), from the "flipper" position close to the horizontal shape (in which the waist muscles are strengthened) can be used; endurance exercise can also be performed by stretching one leg forward and making a "pistol" while sitting with the other leg (this strengthens leg and abdominal muscles).

It should be emphasized that for all four muscle groups - leg, arm, back and abdominal muscle groups, from a hygienic point of view, a normative level of complex power endurance is necessary, because each of them plays a role in maintaining health. plays a certain role. Sufficient strength endurance in the lower back muscles cannot compensate for weakness in the abdominal muscles or vice versa.

To ensure a number of functions of the body - adequate tone of skeletal muscles, massage-corset activity of internal organs, bone, joint system, external respiratory function, peripheral blood and lymph circulation ("peripheral heart") A strong level of endurance, which can provide the appropriate tone of the skeletal muscles necessary to ensure effectiveness, is one of the necessary physical qualities along with general endurance, and is of great importance. Strength endurance training necessary to perform the indicated functions should be carried out with a sufficient level of intensity and serve to effectively develop the morphofunctional properties of transverse muscles. There are two main types of strength endurance. The first of these is static endurance, which is developed with more static (isokinetic) exercises. The second is dynamic endurance, its training is carried out mainly through dynamic (isometric) exercises.

Both types of endurance are necessary for good health. Static tolerance is effective in maintaining muscle tone and performing a massage-corset function for abdominal organs, spine (comfort), heels (prevention of flat heels); dynamic endurance helps the movement of the muscles, the implementation of the "peripheral heart" function. Both types of endurance have a positive effect on the vital activity of muscle tissues, their functional state, energy processes necessary for muscle tissue metabolism, structure and normal functioning of the whole organism.

Strength endurance training is combined with the development of maximum strength and speed-power qualities. Because they are components of strength qualities and have a morphophysiological basis close to them. Their development continues to a certain extent in a parallel form (in this case, it is especially noticeable during physical training sessions for the purpose of health, as long as the cases of differentiation are reflected to a greater extent during sports training) , that is, we can train one of the components of strength and at the same time develop two other types of it, but the specialization of training tools allows us to have an effect on each of them separately.

Results

Strategies are being implemented in our country to develop tourism and services and to include tourism among the ten developed countries of the world. This can be seen from the recent decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This issue is addressed in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4861 dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PF-5308 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 2018 "Strategy of actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" approved by Decree No. It can be seen that a lot of attention is paid to the State Program held in August 16, 2017 No. PQ-3217 "On the first priority measures for the development of the tourism sector in 2018-2019".

On December 31, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev met with the heads of the parliamentary chambers, members of the government, officials of ministries and agencies, summarized the results of the year and defined important tasks for 2020. At this meeting, the most important task in this field was to increase the flow of tourists to 7.5 million in 2020 and to increase the export of services from 1.5 billion dollars.[2]

Although the historical development of tourism in the territory of Uzbekistan has been discussed in some studies, [3:47] the use of the term "new era" in the field of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been ongoing since 2016. is appropriate. It is suggested that there are well-thought-out economic policies and legal foundations behind the rapid reforms in this area.

It should be noted that the base of bilateral agreements in the field of tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan is growing year by year. In particular, in 2013, their number was 45, and in 2018, this figure reached 60 in total. During the analysis of these types of contracts, their general features are shown, and these contracts are divided into two groups in terms of their content, nature and regulation.

First, cooperation agreements on the development of bilateral tourism and agreements regulating relations on humanitarian cooperation;

Second, bilateral agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are separately regulated in the field of tourism services in cooperation agreements.

Today, in our country, the Convention "On Tourism Ethics" signed by the United Nations World Tourism Organization in 2017 requires a new approach to the basic principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Code of Tourism Ethics. Taking into account the fact that the legal foundations of the tourism sector are improving in the international community, the draft Convention "On the Protection of Tourists and International Rights and Obligations of Tourist Services" developed by the United Nations World Tourism Organization and presented to the countries for discussion is also important. In this Convention, the guest and host countries have determined specific tasks before the countries regarding the development of international tourism. The Convention can be a strong legal basis of "Hard Law" character, which regulates mutual cooperation between countries and organizations engaged in tourism activities.

People's interest in learning the way of life, customs and traditions, history and culture of other nations and peoples has been one of the main motivations for traveling for several thousand years. In particular, it was determined that "tourism has become a strategic sector of the republic's economy" [4], and based on the solution of the problem we are researching, "developing tourism infrastructure and creating an acceptable and comfortable tourism culture" [5:6] has become one of the urgent tasks before our state.

The main object of development of the tourism culture of our people at the current stage is the youth. Formation of knowledge and skills of young people in

terms of tourism ethics, travel etiquette, goals of pilgrimage, increasing their knowledge of tourism, expanding their worldview, changing their attitude towards historical monuments is an important factor in the development of tourism culture.

Today, youth tourism is one of the rapidly developing types of tourism and is a broad concept. Youth tourism is defined differently in various foreign literatures, and the World Tourism Organization defines this concept as follows: "A year for people between the ages of 16-29 to learn about the culture and lifestyle of peoples other than their usual living environment, formally and informally." [6] Today, young people traveling around the world are traveling for different purposes, and depending on their purpose, they can be divided into the following types:

One of the most important factors in the development of tourism culture among young people is educational tourism. Educational tourism includes young people to expand their knowledge, study at foreign higher educational institutions for the purpose of obtaining knowledge, and participate in international student exchange programs organized within the framework of institutions.

Pupils and students, employees will have the opportunity to improve their knowledge and skills in educational tourism. Organization of cultural-educational tours, arts and crafts tours, ecotours, religious, wellness tours, adventure tours, as well as festivals, conferences, seminars-trainings, and excursions to museums is a characteristic aspect of this process.

It should be noted that Great Britain is in the leading position in terms of educational tourism development indicators. If at least one million people come here a year, in 2017-2018, 750,000 students (tourists) visited, and an average profit of 6 billion dollars was received from them. Another example is the state of Israel. If any of the foreign citizens who want to study here is Jewish, they will be given the opportunity to study on the basis of a grant. Studying in Finland is done only on the basis of grants from the state, and accommodation, meals and other expenses are carried out at the students' own expense. [7]

The development of recreational tourism, pilgrimage and ecological tourism in our country gives a great impetus to the development of economic development and social spheres.

One of the most important foundations for the development of tourism culture in our country is educational foundations. Especially in this regard, it is time to take important steps in the development of tourism culture based on the

training of modern personnel for the ecotourism direction of the tourism sector. There are many favorable areas for the formation of ecotourism in the territory of our republic. For example, taking into account the geographical location and historical past of the Samarkand region, the following settlements can be included in the ecoregions to be established: settlements in the city of Urgut, where thousand-year-old maple trees grow, miraculous holes located on the road to Amonqo'ton, the geographical location of this settlement and its areas rich in environmentally friendly fruits are among them.

The colorful courtyards planted with flowers, the rural life rich in Uzbek traditions of our nation will serve as an important factor for the establishment of modern ecotourism, and it will be possible to turn into attractive places of interest. In general, for the development of eco-tourism and agro-tourism, there are a lot of geographical areas in the republic, it is necessary to identify them, train and increase the number of specialists who are geographically knowledgeable, who understand ecological education and culture. There are specialists in various fields in our country, but the number of specialists in the field of tourism and ecology is limited, the reason for this is the lack of demand for specialists in this field. [8:347]

It can be said that there are some obstacles in the development of eco- and agro-tourism, because the population and the guides lack experience in this field. "Silk Road" International Tourism University, Paris Academy of France, Sahid Tourism Institute (Indonesia), Sochi State University, etc.

Tourism is the main source of income for the state budget in many countries of the world. It may be promising to organize scientifically based routes of ecotourism in historical monuments, monuments, springs, maples, inscriptions on stones, nature reserves, "Jayron" eco-center, national parks.

Today, for the first time, the creation of the "Road map" for the formation of eco- and agro-tourism is being implemented in our republic. At the beginning of this work, specialists from various fields have started work, but the first task remains the issue of personnel. In higher education institutions, it is necessary to include enough hours of ecology and geography lessons in the curriculum, to educate young specialists in ecological culture and in-depth geographical knowledge. Using new technologies to form ecotourism and bring it to the level of "clustering" will give positive results.

The main goal of the adoption of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" and the "Concept of Development of the Higher Education System until 2030" is the democratic changes and market reforms of

the personnel training system. non-compliance with the requirements, inability of the current educational system to meet the requirements of today, insufficient material-technical and information base of the educational process, lack of quality educational-methodical and scientific literature and didactic materials, educational system, lack of mutual cooperation and mutually beneficial integration between science and production, teachers' lack of modern knowledge, skills and qualifications that enable them to provide students with modern knowledge, lack of highly qualified pedagogic personnel, personnel It is explained by the fact that it aims to eliminate serious deficiencies in the existing system of training.[8:19]

Discussion

The teacher plays the main role in eliminating the shortcomings mentioned above. Therefore, the successful solution of these problems depends on the professional and pedagogical training of future teachers.[9:47]

In this regard, it is appropriate to teach "Tourism ethics and culture" to undergraduate students. The main task of this subject is to reveal the complex relationship between society and nature, to create knowledge, skills and abilities in tourism and ecotourism in students, and it should be focused on solving the following tasks. In particular:

- by developing the theoretical foundations of students' knowledge, skills and abilities in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette, justifying the actual pedagogical importance of the problem;
- to sufficiently inculcate the formation of knowledge, qualifications and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette into the current curriculum, programs and textbooks;
- development of technologies for pedagogical assessment of the essence of the methods and approaches used in the process of formation of knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette and the principles of its selection;
- on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, to determine the interactive methods of creating knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette in students, to develop the methodology of their implementation and to apply them to the educational process in a timely manner;- development of practical-methodical recommendations on the formation of knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette in students;

- to inculcate in students the ideas of patriotism, love for nature and respect for it by creating knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette;

- the successful solution of the problems of tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette in students, regardless of the field occupied by future young professionals, will help to create the existence, the civilization created by the peoples and states in it, owned and allows to form sufficient ideas about the nature that is obliged to protect.

For this purpose, in order to organize the educational process and increase the knowledge, skills and abilities of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette, and to eliminate the noted problems in their professional training:

- taking into account the state and social orders, conducting research on the formation of knowledge, skills and skills of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette, modernizing educational paradigms and developing solutions to conceptual problems;

- formation of clear visions of future specialists in the formation of knowledge, skills and skills in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette;

- acquisition of special requirements and necessary professional knowledge, qualifications and skills that allow organizing professional activity based on the requirements of society and social development;

- mastering the formation of knowledge, qualifications and skills related to the special level of professional training - tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette;

- to decide on an innovative approach that is the basis for the development and improvement of knowledge, skills and skills of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette.

Conclusion

This process, in turn, increases the social prestige of tourism culture and serves to create a national model of personnel training. The successful solution of these tasks, in turn, is an important factor in the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of future specialists in tourism, ecotourism, tourism ethics, travel etiquette.

In short, the organizational-methodical component of the technology of developing volitional qualities in physical education requires a reflexive point of

view in future physical education teachers and creates an opportunity to develop volitional qualities based on a competency approach.

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